

Physical exercise versus psychopathologies in some chronic diseases

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Abstract

Chronic diseases affect children and adults alike. They may involve a typically physical aspect but also the human psyche. Statistics show that there has been an increase in the incidence of chronic diseases over the past years, thus leading to the intensification of such effects as the avoidance of daily activities or social roles, mainly due to physical limitations. The paper attempts to present the psychopathologies present in some of the chronic diseases, as well as the interdependence between such psychopathologies and physical activity. There are references to studies that provide proof for both positive and negative impact of stress on the performance of physical activities. Attention was also drawn to issues that may be crucial in the case where physical exercise is limited in chronically ill patients.

Keywords: psychopathology, chronic disease, physical activity

Introduction

Over the past years, the incidence rate of chronic diseases has increased and particular attention has been paid not only to their physical aspect, but also to the mental issues accompanying a given chronic condition. The mental stress of patients resulting, amongst others, from decreased physical efficiency makes them avoid their daily activities and social roles due to physical limitations [1]. Numerous reports confirm the occurrence of psychopathologies in the course of chronic diseases [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. A number of publications point towards a positive influence of physical exercise on patients' well-being and psychopathological symptoms [6, 7, 8, 9].

Psychopathologies in chronic diseases

Self-esteem is defined as "the evaluation of the self, or a generalised, relatively stable perception of self as a person" [10]. Rosenberg [11] distinguishes two dimensions of self-esteem: high (a positive attitude towards oneself), where individuals are convinced that they are good and worthy people, and low (a negative attitude towards oneself), where individuals think of themselves in negative terms as well as experience dissatisfaction with themselves and their own achievements. Another definition of self-esteem describes it as "the attitude towards oneself, especially towards one's own possibilities and other features of social value" [12]. Individuals with low self-esteem often face the risk of depressive disorders [11] or anxiety disturbances, have little faith in their own

potential, as well as are sceptical and critical of the world and other people. Low self-esteem also results in lower capability to cope with life difficulties [13]. Therefore, self-esteem is regarded as a permanent trait rather than a temporary state [14].

K.R. Fox [15] as well as J.C. Spence and P. Poon [16] reviewed scientific studies to determine the influence of physical effort on self-esteem. Both opinions demonstrated little association between physical activity and overall self-perception.

Compared to healthy subjects, patients with diagnosed depression manifest lower self-esteem [17].

The American Psychiatric Association defines depression as a psychiatric disorder, a clinically significant syndrome and a behavioural or psychological pattern observed in a given individual. It is related to the experienced suffering, pain or a higher risk of death. Irrespective of the initial cause of this syndrome, at a given moment it is a manifestation of a psychological, biological or behavioural dysfunction [18]. Depression is very often accompanied by reduced mental and physical activity, which is caused by the cerebral centres of regulation, activity and activation. The slowness affects thinking and the speed of speech, lower concentration and attention, the ability and speed of decision-making processes, the loss of energy and strength as well as chronic physical fatigue. These symptoms cause depressive patients to be considered lazy. This, in turn, intensifies their feeling of guilt, which may lead to an increase in suicidal thoughts. Their permanent fatigue makes it impossible to perform

the simplest activities. The daily household chores and professional tasks are becoming increasingly difficult [19,20].

Due to the growing incidence rate of chronic diseases in recent years, particular attention has been paid not only to their physical but also mental aspect. This is caused by the psychological burden of patients, resulting from – amongst others – reduced physical fitness. Patients feel incapable of performing their daily activities and social roles due to physical limitation, the need of continuous treatment and the required adaptation to the new situation, as well as the necessity to change their lifestyles (e.g. a diet, systematic physical activity). Moreover, the awareness of constantly being “a patient” may have a negative impact on the person’s psyche, particularly in the case of young and active individuals. Such a state of affairs may entail new limitations, reduce expectations of the future, undermine self-esteem and even lead to depression [1].

Existing data suggest that depressive symptoms may occur in patients with PAD (peripheral artery disease) [2,3] as a result of functional disorders [2], decreased vascular patency [3] and low quality of life [4]. Unfortunately, long-term studies concerning the occurrence and course of PAD-related depressive symptoms are still missing [2].

The Center of Research on Psychology in Somatic Diseases is one of the first to have conducted studies on patients with diagnosed PAD, related to the coexistence of lower extremity symptoms and the mental state (anxiety, depressive symptoms, anhedonia). Anxiety, depressive symptoms and anhedonia were intense and differed significantly depending on the severity of the lower extremity discomfort reported by the patients. Those individuals who experienced pain at rest were more likely to manifest more severe mental disturbances. Patients with atypical post-activity symptoms also exhibited greater anxiety compared to asymptomatic patients [5].

Different conclusions were drawn by E. Ponte and S. Cattinelli, who indicated little influence of intermittent claudication on the patients’ psyche. The researchers argued that this might be caused by the specific nature of the disease, which – despite being described as serious – does not affect the “most vital” organs such as the eyes, the heart or the brain. They also drew attention to the average age of the patients, which was over 60 years,

suggesting that it was one of the reasons why the patients accepted their disease. The authors claim that the sense of belonging to a specific age group leads to deliberate abandonment of certain social roles and cessation of pursuing the roles reserved for the young [1].

A study conducted by Mary McGrae Mc Dermott et al. revealed that PAD patients demonstrating higher scores on the Geriatric Depression Scale Short Form (GDS-S), that is experiencing more intense depressive symptoms, achieved shorter distances in a 6-minute marching test compared to PAD patients who demonstrated lower GDS-S scores. The relationship between a higher number of depressive symptoms and worse functioning of the lower extremity was independent of any concomitant diseases, ABI and other potential disruptors. The authors suggest that ischaemia of the lower extremity, as well as the related functional limitation and pain, may produce depressive symptoms in PAD patients. Moreover, individuals with this disease who exhibit depressive symptoms are less likely to pursue a healthy lifestyle involving physical activity and smoking cessation, and this may lead to greater disability in PAD. It is worth noting that there is currently a lack of convincing studies indicating the cause-and-effect direction in the relationship between depressive symptoms and functional disturbances in PAD sufferers. Similarly, no definite conclusion has been reached as to whether the treatment of depressive symptoms is linked to the improvement in lower limb functioning in this group of patients [21].

An interesting relation was also presented in the findings of a study concerning chronic diseases in children. The study assessed psychopathologies and self-esteem in 60 children (including 30 epilepsy sufferers and 30 thalassaemic patients). The findings revealed, amongst others, that behavioural problems, anger or fear were more common in the former group. Thalassaemia, on the other hand, led to sadness and a lack of interest in life. The depression subscale was at its highest in the case of both diseases. This emphasises the importance to pay attention to a chronic disease, which – if present in children – can negatively affect both their physical and mental condition from an early age onwards. [22].

The most common psychopathologies have been presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Psychopathologies

It is important, as early as upon diagnosis of a chronic disease, to note what kind of pathologies the patient may be exposed to.

The impact of physical exercise on psychopathologies

The reduction in the intensity of depressive symptoms and certain states of anxiety following the application of physical exercise raises the question of whether physical activity can be used for alleviating the symptoms of mental disorders [23]. It is generally recognised that physical activity and exercise have a positive impact on the mood, anxiety and depression. A great number of studies describe the relationship between physical activity and general well-being [6,7,8,9].

Cross-sectional studies invariably associate high levels of physical activity with better mental health. They point to the link between systematic exercise and low-level depressive symptoms amongst both the youth [6] and the elderly [7].

Physical activity in everyday life measured by the International Physical Activity Questionnaire, IPAQ) was associated with the self-perception of general health [8] as well as with the self-perception of mental health [9]. The questionnaire encompassed the total of 16,230 respondents over the age of 14 years, demonstrating a relationship between the application of physical activity and mental health.

Analysing the data from the US National Survey, R.D. Goodwin [24] found a significant link between regu-

lar physical activity and lower incidence of major depression, social phobia, specific phobia and agoraphobia. The positive effect of exercise persisted regardless of the socio-demographic characteristics, the physical disorders reported and the concomitant mental disturbances. W.J. Strawbridge et al. [25] described the protective influence of physical activity on the development of depression in the elderly. Having examined 1,900 patients for the period of 8 years, M.E. Farmer et al. [26] proved that regular exercise reduces the risk of developing depression.

However, more recent studies put an emphasis on the fact that depressive symptoms may occur in patients with PAD [2,3] due to functional disorders [2], decreased vascular patency [3] and low quality of life resulting from the negative impact of the disease, amongst others, on physical fitness [4]. Many authors confirm that patients with intermittent claudication experience a lower quality of life [29, 30]. The occurrence of depressive symptoms is also supported by the study conducted at the Center of Research on Psychology in Somatic Diseases on patients with diagnosed PAD, related to the coexistence of lower extremity symptoms and the mental state (anxiety, depressive symptoms, anhedonia) [5].

The arguments in favour of long-term training are provided by the results presented by other authors. M.E. Farmer examined 1,900 patients for the period of 8 years, proving that regular exercise reduces the risk of developing depression [26]. Similarly, R.W. Motl et al. [27] reported that the naturally occurring changes in physical activity are inversely proportional to depressive symp-

toms in the early youth. However, after 4 years of studies on a sample consisting of 2,548 adolescents and young adults, it was found that patients engaged in regular physical activity exhibited a significantly lower incidence of any mental disorders, including concomitant ones, as well as less frequent states of anxiety (Strohle et al. 2007 [28]).

A similar conclusion is provided by E. Ponte and S. Cattinelli, whose study found a significant relationship between illness, especially chronic conditions, and lower self-esteem. M. Rosenberg underlines that individuals with lower self-esteem are prone to depressive and anxiety disorders. Therefore, longer observation of the patients is indicated. Low self-esteem may lead to lower ability to cope with difficulties and critical perception of the world and other people [11, 13]. Interesting conclusions were presented by J.E. Roberts and S.M. Monroe, who took into account the general, theoretical role of self-perception in depression. They confirmed that low self-esteem is often considered a risk factor that increases the susceptibility of developing depression. However, relevant studies failed to unequivocally prove its predictive nature. It was suggested that higher susceptibility to depression occurs in individuals whose self-esteem is unstable and changeable [31].

An interesting study was also conducted by E. Speyer et al., who assessed the influence of adapted physical activity sessions in the hospital on health-related quality of life in children with cancer [32]. To assess the efficacy of adapted physical activity (APA) on health-related quality of life (HRQoL) of 30 hospitalised children and adolescents with cancer between 9 and 18 years of age. Children and parents completed the child and parent forms. The results show that APA during hospitalisation for children with cancer was associated with better HRQoL for most of the HRQoL psychological and physical dimensions.

Yet another study that is worth mentioning due to the extensive sample group (over 40,400 subjects) concerns the anti-depressive and anti-fatigue effects of physical effort. To explore the two-way relationship between physical activity and frequent mental disorders, as well as to determine the importance of context, type and intensity of the activity undertaken, an analysis was conducted on the subjects' responses related to physical effort (its frequency and intensity) performed during leisure time and at work. Depression and anxiety were measured using the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS). There was an inverse relationship between the amount of leisure-time physical activity and case-level symptoms of depression. This association was only present with leisure-time (as opposed to workplace) activity and was not dependent on the intensity of activities undertaken. Higher levels

of social support and social engagement were significant in explaining the relationship between leisure activity and depression.

Subjects who engage in regular leisure-time activity of any intensity are less likely to have symptoms of depression. The context and social benefits of physical activity are important in explaining this relationship [33].

The positive influence of physical exercise may also be perceived from a strictly biochemical perspective. S. Moylana et al. examined how inflammation, oxidative and nitrogen stress (O&NS) mediates the beneficial effect of physical activity on anxiety disorder symptoms and behaviours. The authors stress that regular physical activity exerts a positive influence on the symptoms related to anxiety disorders, even though the biological mechanisms underlying this phenomenon are not yet fully known. A great number of study results support inflammation and O&NS as important in the pathogenesis of mood and anxiety disorders, and physical activity is known to influence these same pathways. The authors analysed the interdependency of anxiety disorders, physical activity, inflammatory condition and O&NS in order to examine whether modulation of inflammation and O&NS may partially strengthen the positive influence of physical activity on anxiety disorders. Numerous studies support the notion that physical activity operates as an anti-inflammatory and anti-O&NS agent which potentially exerts positive effects on neuroplasticity, the expression of neurotrophins and normal neuronal functions. [34].

The influence of a chronic disease on physical activity

A number of papers present physical activity as the golden mean, exerting a positive influence on the physical and psychological well-being of people. The current trend is to promote participation in sport and exercise amongst both the young and the elderly, men and women, as well as healthy individuals and those dealing with some disease-related symptoms. The question that needs to be answered is why some diagnoses effectively impede physical therapy. Several studies provide an interesting description of how a chronic disease may affect the patients' willingness to take up physical activity.

In the case of chronic fatigue syndrome (CFS) or fibromyalgia, physical activity often causes severe exacerbation of the related symptoms. Patients may feel much worse following exercise, which makes it seem reasonable that they will try to avoid factors that increase the negative consequences of their illness. The fear of physical activity is stronger than the potential benefits of rehabilitation or recreational activities. The review carried out by Jo Nijis and his colleagues included results proving that fear and avoidance of movement is widespread amongst

CFS and FM patients. This is also related to the differences in clinical features, the course of the disease, the intensification of symptoms, as well as self-esteem, quality of life and the issue of disability [35].

Another study compared physical efficiency in patients with schizophrenia and their healthy counterparts. Obesity had a significant negative impact on the distance covered. However, schizophrenic patients achieved shorter distances than healthy subjects. Dyspnoea was common in schizophrenic individuals, especially those with concomitant obesity. A conclusion to be drawn from the study is that functional exercise capacity in patients with schizophrenia is reduced not only by obesity, perceived discomfort and pain, but also by a sedentary, unhealthy lifestyle and a reduced physical self-perception [36].

Even though it is believed that stress and physical activity are interrelated, the majority of papers analysing this relationship are dedicated to the exploration of exercise as a stress-relieving instrument. A smaller set of studies is focused on how stress affects activity. An extensive review related to this subject was carried out by Stults-Kolehmainen and Sinha. Their work indicates that some papers present severe stress as the cause of a significant reduction in physical activity (behavioural inhibition) along with an increase in sedentary lifestyle. An interesting phenomenon highlighted in a number of studies is the proof that stress has a positive impact on physical activity (behavioral activation). It comes as no surprise that many people cope with their difficult situations and problems through physical exercise. Future works should be focused on a theory that could explain the mechanisms underlying the different types of stress and its effects on physical activity [37].

Summary

A chronic disease affects patients for many years, and often throughout their lives, usually changing the intensity of its symptoms over time. It has a number of negative consequences which a given sufferer must cope with on a daily basis. In the case of most long-term diseases, one of the treatment methods or methods of supporting treatment is physiotherapy and physical activity. An illness that significantly hinders physical exercise is a great problem. The essence of a properly administered therapy is to detect psychopathologies that may appear in patients and encourage them to take up physical activity as well as apply measures and actions minimising such possibilities. Since a chronic disease often cannot be cured/suppressed and its symptoms are long-term in nature, patients sometimes lose motivation and do not see the point of the ongoing treatment, because they are aware it will not produce the desired effects. If this is the

case, then it is important to make it clear to them that, even though the disease itself cannot be eradicated, it is possible to control and minimise its symptoms and consequences. A chronic disease poses a very great challenge, because it involves a series of negative phenomena. Therefore, each patient should be treated on an individual basis. The characteristics of chronic diseases and their related pathologies are wide-ranging and continuously supplemented, thus making it worth to keep track of the current reports on the subject.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.